

Equivalent impact set-up for lightning strike damage on composite coupons

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ABSTRACT

Lightning strikes of composite materials induce two distinct kinds of direct effects: surface and bulk mechanical damage. Bulk damage includes fiber-resin debonding, transverse cracks, fiber rupture and ply delamination. It results from the mechanical stresses associated to physical processes which come with lightning strikes such as surface explosion or magnetic force generation. We propose a method to design mechanical impact tests representative of lightning tests in the sense that strains and stresses applied to the material in both experimental situations are comparable. A campaign of actual equivalent mechanical impact tests has been designed using a simulation driven procedure and performed in the laboratory. The procedure uses the expected rear face deflections as the control parameter of the energy transfer. The performance of the method of equivalence is demonstrated through the comparison of numerical and real impact tests observations with lightning strikes measurements of rear face displacements and internal damaged areas.

1 INTRODUCTION

Extending the use of composite materials to aircrafts structures exposed to lightning strike (fuselage, wings) demands specific designs for conducting high current flows; the mass optimization of these protections has become an industrial challenge. Lightning strike on composite materials induces two distinct kinds of direct effects: surface and bulk damage. Surface damage involves paint and protection removal which can extent to the CFRP first plies located near the lightning zone. Bulk damage includes fiber-resin debonding, transverse cracks, fiber rupture and ply delamination through the entire depth of the structure. Bulk damages result from the association of various physical processes arising from the lightning strike such as surface explosion or magnetic force generation. These core damages have been compared to pure mechanical damage from impact tests and revealed to be quite similar. The strong resemblance of lightning core damage with traditional impact one leads us to assume an important mechanical part in the damage process from lightning strike. Previous studies have investigated such analogy with mechanical impacts [1], privileging injected energy (delivered by electrical or kinetic sources) and induced projected surface damage as criteria to be sought for assessing equivalence. Such attempts face a main issue since most part of dissipated energy during a lightning strike does not participate in damaging the material. We then propose another method to design mechanical impact tests representative of lightning tests.

The analogy between the lightning strike energy deposit on the complete target (coating, protection and laminate) and the equivalent mechanical impact relies on the transferred impulse responsible for the rear face kinematics. The mechanical impact is done on the nude composite plate alone (without surface coverage). The representativeness of the equivalent impact tests is assessed by maximum values of rear face deflections and velocities at a so-called ‘strike time’ [4-7] during lightning and mechanical tests. It is shown that the mechanical impact leads to damage distributions very similar to lightning strikes’ ones in most of the cases. Fundamental differences in damage distributions and rear face behaviors arise for unpainted structures.

The present paper is organized as follows: in section 2, we present the equivalent mechanical parameters and test set-up on nude composite plates along with the associated lightning tests on complete plates (composite and surface coverage). In section 3, we present the obtained results through mechanical impact tests compared to the numerical predictions as well as the associated lightning strike results for both rear face displacement and C-scan analysis.

2 EQUIVALENT MECHANICAL TESTS

The aim of this study is to design a mechanical test that would induce observable phenomenon equivalent to lightning strikes. Indeed, lightning strike tests are complicated, expensive and involve various kinds of physics such as electromagnetism and electro-thermal effects that are not yet properly quantified. By using a pure mechanical impact, we propose a simpler, more reproducible method as well as results that are more easily acknowledgeable.

2.1 Equivalent parameters for mechanical tests

In our study we decided to focus on the transferred impulse k (N.s). It has been shown in a previous paper [10] that this impulse can be experimentally related to a plateau value of rear face displacement versus time. The plateau value is reached at the lightning strike time (so called short time) at which the rear face velocity reaches a maximum value during the lightning strike. Classical short time values are about $100\mu\text{s}$. The plateau value is called ‘d infinite’ and can be defined such as:

$$d_{\infty} = k / (8(\mu D))^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

Where μ is the mass per unit surface and D the bending stiffness of the plate. Then we can also write the following equivalence:

$$k = m \times v \quad (2)$$

As a preliminary approach, it is assumed that impactors are spherical, made out of steel, do not deform, and hit the target normally. It is thus possible to find the proper values of mass and speed for an equivalent mechanical projectile. From previously performed lightning campaigns, several lightning strike samples with various paint and protection designs were selected in order to study the influence of paint and protection on the obtained damaged. The samples differ by their surface states only: they are covered with expanded copper foils of mass 195 g/m^2 (ECF195) and can be painted with different thicknesses from $50\mu\text{m}$ (P50) up to $200\mu\text{m}$ (P200). For each of these samples, presented in the table 1, the equivalent projectile’s mass and speed that provided the best result in term of rear face deflection were calculated using equations (1) and (2), as shown on figure1.

Lightning samples	Surface state (paint + protection)	Calculated speed (m/s)	Projectile mass (g)
101	ECF195-P160	72	4
103	ECF195-P50	60	4
107	ECF195-P160	80	4

Table 1: Characteristics of the equivalent mechanical projectile to the associated lightning strikes

2.2 Numerical model

The ABAQUS-explicit Finite Element software is used to determine the behavior of nude composite plates subjected to the impact by projectiles. The computed mass and velocities for the different lightning samples are presented in table 1. The model is a probe concept used to drive the real experimental impact set-up design and help placing gages and optical measurement devices. The model represents the square 400*400 mm² samples, the clock-like clamped boundary conditions as in the lightning strike tests, and the projectile. The impactor is modelled as an analytical rigid body (analytical sphere). It is assigned an initial mass and a perpendicular velocity and is positioned above the center of the plate. A penalty contact without friction and damping is defined between the projectile and the target. For these preliminary stages, when designing an impact configuration equivalent to strikes, composite samples are modelled using shell elements (S4R), under the hypothesis of small perturbations and are set a homogenized elastic orthotropic material following the classical lamination theory. The mesh is composed of rectangular elements in majority. Due to the sample geometry and in order to reduce the computation time, a progressive refinement mesh is prescribed from the boundaries toward the center of the plate.

Figure 1: ¼ of the numerical model meshing strategy

The overall shape of the numerical deflections is as expected: a rapid increase at short times controlled by the speed of the impactor, and a constant value at larger time such that the plate can be assumed infinite (Figure 2). We can see that the numerical model shows a very good approximation with lightning strike tests at short times ($<100\mu\text{s}$). At larger times the influence of the surface behavior is more important. Our shell model is not able to reproduce this effect on the global deflection of the plate. Some explanations of this have been given in a previous paper [10]. However this simple shell model is able to reproduce both the speed and the amplitude of the rear face deflection of the samples stroke by lightning and thus confirmed that our approach is valid. Experimental tests are then needed to fully validate the method.

Figure 2: Comparison of rear face deflections between lightning strike (dotted line) and numerical simulation with a steel projectile (plain line)

2.3 Mechanical set up

Mechanical impact tests were conducted using a 4g steel sphere projectile, launched by a gas gun apparatus (canon) in a range of velocities from 50 to 150m/s. The canon is located at the Institut Clément Ader Laboratory (ICA) in Toulouse, France. The impacted samples are carbon-epoxy square plates of 400*400 mm² also fabricated at the ICA. The plates are made of 8 plies of CFRP with the following sequence [45/0/-45/90]s.

Figure 3: Gas gun apparatus: left complete set-up with the pressure vessel; right: the metallic boundary ring on which is fixed the target square plate

The mechanical set up was designed to represent the experimental conditions of the lightning strike tests. A metallic ring has been fabricated in order to reproduce the peculiar clocklike clamping system of the plate, with twelve bolts disposed in a circle of diameter $\Phi 370\text{mm}$, see figure 3. The set-up is equipped with a high speed camera which allows measuring the projectile velocity at the exit of the gas gun. The rear face displacements are measured using two displacement sensors (Keyence 20kHz without contact).

Comparisons between the computed velocities of the equivalent mechanical projectiles and the mechanical impact speeds measured during the experiments are shown on Table2.

Lightning sample	Expected projectile speed (m/s)	Associated mechanical sample	Obtained projectile speed (ms)
101	72	2	75
103	60	3	65
107	80	8	81

Table 2: Obtained versus desired speeds of the equivalent projectiles during gas gun impact tests

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results under consideration are at first the rear face displacements and velocities in numerical and experimental impact tests versus lightning strikes' ones (figure 5). It is shown that the equivalent impact gives quite good results for the time duration under interest, that is for short times ($<100\mu\text{s}$). Numerical and experimental impacts give almost the same behavior even after (figure 4).

In a second step damages measured in the samples after impact tests are compared with damages created after the corresponding lightning strike (figures 7 and 8). It is shown that delaminated areas are of the same order of magnitude except for lightened samples covered by a thin layer of paint. Both kinds of comparison are discussed further.

3.1 Global behavior: rear face displacement

At first we compare the predictions of the numerical model with the test curves obtained during the campaign in figure 4. We can see that the experimental curves are in good agreement with the numerical predictions for both speed and deflection at short and larger times as well for all the different speeds obtained during the campaign.

Figure 4: Validation of the method by comparison of mechanical impact result with numerically predicted one for impact at 70 and 65 m/s.

The mechanical impacts provide, in each case, a slightly higher rear face deflection compared to the numerical predictions (about 4% at 72 m/s and 8% at 65 m/s). This result is coherent with the use of a homogenized elastic shell model which does not take into account damage induced by the impact. It is noticed that impacts at 65 and 72 m/s give approximately the same maximum value of deflection at short times, and that the deflection is maintained during a longer period at 65 m/s ($50\mu\text{s}$) than at 72 m/s ($20\mu\text{s}$). While the numerical model is too simplistic to represent these details, at these two impact velocities, the max peak of deflection is always approached by the model with a precision that is acceptable and the general behavior of the plate also. This satisfying correlation proved that our modelling strategy of the mechanical impact is relevant.

In a second time the same comparison is made with the lightning strike results, as shown in figure 5. The equivalent mechanical impacts provide quite good results at short times with lightning strikes results for samples 103 and 107: the initial slope of the curve is well reproduced as well as the first peak of deflection (see figure 5 right). The mechanical impact fails at reproducing the large time deflection of lightning and the value of the constant deflection is smaller in the impact models than in the strike measurements. This difference is concordant with the previous observations between lightning curves and the numerical model made in [10] and confirms that in the case of painted samples with a thick layer the surface states influence the structural response of the impacted panels and that the numerical model and our equivalent impact are only fully representative in the case of samples with small thicknesses of paint. The perturbation of paint also explains the strong difference for sample 101: in the lightning strike test, the paint was burned on a very small part at the root attachment and so disturbed very soon the global behavior of the plate so that the paint cover was maintained from the first stages of the lightning process, whereas for sample 107 the central zone was unpainted on a spot zone of a few 10 mm in diameter so that its effect is delayed in time.

Figure 5: Comparison of mechanical impact result with numerically predicted one and lightning strikes results for the three cases

The displacement and maximum velocities at $50\mu\text{s}$ (mean instant of maximum velocity in lightning strikes) are compared in table 3.

Lightning samples	LS displacement (μm)	Mech. Impact displ. (μm)	Relative difference	LS max. velocity (m/s)	Mech. Impact max. vel. (m/s)	Relative difference
101	2827	2159	-23.6%	37.4	33.6	-10.1%
103	1726	1914	+10.8%	25.6	33.8	+32%
107	2626	2262	-13.8%	32.3	35.4	+9.6%

Table 3: displacements and maximum velocities at $50\mu\text{s}$

Displacement prediction of case 101 is about 24%, which again is attributed to the effect of the paint effect during the lightning test. For cases 103 and 107 errors on displacement predictions are about 10% and 14% which is acceptable. On the contrary, the velocity prediction of case 101 is quite good while for case 103 the error is about 32%. This very high value is attributed to the fact that the displacement evolution is not similar in the lightning strike test and in the mechanical test. This is attributed to the confinement effect of gas generated by the metallic cover explosion. As long as we are concerned by composite panels covered by layers of paint that are burned during lightning test, our mechanical impacts are considered successful at reproducing the rear face displacement and velocities induced by lightning strikes at short times. As the representativeness of our equivalent impact tests is made on the comparison of these two kinematics quantities, and for short times, our method is validated by this experimental campaign.

3.2 Local behavior: damage surface

To go further in our equivalence and regarding the limitations of the equivalent mechanical concept for displacements and velocities at large times, an analysis of the damage induced by both lightning strike and mechanical impacts is conducted. To do so, ultrasonic C-scans analyses are conducted on the associated samples. Table 4 presents the total delaminated area measured for each lightning strike and its associated mechanical impact, and the relative difference. Mechanical impacts provide relevant values of delaminated areas compared to lightning strikes (LS), except for sample 103. Sample 103 presents zero damage for the lightning C-scans which is relevant with the little thickness of paint layer on the surface, as it was proven that the bigger the thickness of paint, the higher the damage due to lightning strike. The corresponding mechanical impact generates a delamination.

Lightning samples	Associated mechanical samples	Projectile's speed (m/s)	LS delaminated area (mm ²)	Mechanical delaminated area (mm ²)	Relative difference
101	2	75	2321	2036	-12%
103	3	65	0	689	-
107	8	81	1711	1672	-2%

Table 4: delaminated area for lightning strikes and associated mechanical impacts

After comparing the delaminated area measured by ultrasonic C-scans, a comparison is made on the actual C-scans measured from the rear face. Indeed for lightning strike samples, the impacted side of the plates were too damaged to produce correct ultrasonic scans, and the protection layers caused perturbations. Figure 6 presents the method used to analyse the scans obtained.

Figure 6: Two scales for ultrasonic testing method: left the thickness, right the fiber orientation

We compare in figure 7 the results of the mechanical impact at 75 m/s which corresponds to the lightning samples 101, which is considered as being the poorest comparison case and which is expected to give more information thus. The comparison of the two scans shows several differences. First, the dimensions and shapes of the two damage areas are quite different but give the same order of total surface, as shown on figure 7 and in table 4. The damages obtained with LS are larger than those obtain with the equivalent mechanical impact. The lightning strike damage area presents a very peculiar shape made of two zones articulated around a 90° oriented delamination between the plies 3 (-45°) and 4 (90°). On the contrary, the ultrasonic scan of the mechanical impact presents characteristic features of a mechanical impact: a butterfly shape with a central vertical symmetry axis that this the axis of the projectile displacement, the wings of the butterfly being separated by two distinct visible cracks; the wings are limited by two series of cracks oriented on the fibre's direction of the underlying ply (length) and of the upper lying ply (width). The large splinter oriented along the last ply orientation is typical of high speed mechanical impact and is a feature that we rarely encounter in lightning strike C-scans. The butterfly shape of the delaminated area with its wings on both sides of a large 90° oriented delamination between the plies 3 and 4 (-45/90) also is a current feature of this kind of impact, as shown on figure 8. The distribution of damage through the thickness is also different between the two impacts. For lightning strike, the damage seems always to stop at the double 90° interface and thus the damage area is confined in the first half of the thickness of the laminate. The mechanical impacts on the other hand generate damage through all the thickness of the laminate and finish with the large splinter on the rear face of the samples.

Figure 7: ultrasonic scans for lightning strike (left) and associated mechanical impact (right) at 75m/s for sample 101 at interface between plies 3 (-45°) and 4 (90°)

Figure 8: ultrasonic scans for mechanical impact at 75m/s

From all the above analysis, it is demonstrated that our equivalent mechanical impact allows

reproducing with accuracy the rear face displacement of a composite thin plate submitted to a lightning strike until the peak of deflection for nude or slightly painted samples, as well as the total damage area created by such a shock for slightly painted samples. These observations are used as a basis to validate the proposed equivalence method. By pushing forward our analysis, it was decided to put the damage distribution of the equivalent mechanical impact to the test. The comparison with lightning strike damage C-scans showed that the mechanical impacts generate damage trough the sample thickness that differ with those obtained after a lightning strike test. Except for interfaces that hide the next interfaces, C-Scans can be used to quantify properly the difference of damage distribution for each interface. Direct measures of delamination extent in each interface are possible using microscopic observations on cut samples. This result is very useful since it gives qualitative and quantitative information about the mechanical contribution of the energy in a lightning strike, and it also gives an idea of the interaction between the covering paint versus time. It demonstrates that rear face displacements and velocities are mainly due to the mechanical part of the loading, while damage inside the samples thickness result from both this structural reaction and the interaction with the paint confinement.

Differences between mechanical impacts and lightning strikes damage are mainly due to the type of impulse created by the local contact of a small and hard projectile. Indeed, as a first attempt of analysis, it has been decided to use a steel ball of 4g mass and $\phi 9.8\text{mm}$ diameter. This small projectile launched at relative high speeds (about 70m/s) is known to create craters and rear face splinters localized around the projectile contact zone: surface craters appear, then by increasing the impact velocity, penetration and perforation. Even if splinters also arise during lightning, they are not due to the same load distributions. In fact, the electrical arc expands radially during the strike and our steel ball is not able to reproduce such behaviour. At larger times, the deflection plateau observed during lightning strike tests was not well reproduced by the mechanical impact for the same reasons.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The present work is a first attempt to design a mechanical impact test representative of a lightning direct effect test in the loading phase where damage increase up to a maximum. The analogy is made on rear face measurement of deflections and maximum speed during lightning strike and mechanical tests. An equivalent impact using a simple analytical model has been designed and checked with numerical models. Several results arise from this study such as the representativeness of the impact which is better for slightly painted samples at short times. Actual canon test were performed to validate the numerical predictions as well as our equivalence method. The results were very satisfying regarding the kinematics of the sample. Indeed the canon tests results provide good correlation with the predictive numerical model and the lightning strike results at short times for rear face displacements and velocities. During the short times period, differences between mechanical impacts and lightning strikes are essentially damage distribution in thickness. From comparison of the obtained damage in both experimental conditions using C-scans or micro-cuts, we have shown that the equivalent mechanical impacts provided concordant total damage surfaces with lightning strike damage results but could not provide identical distribution of the damage through the plies and the thickness of the plate. These observations stated that our preliminary hypothesis (spherical rigid impactor) should be revised for improved representativeness of time and space distributions of incident kinetic energy. Simultaneously, the numerical model is to be improved to integrate damage modes and thus predict the damage mechanisms and area to be compared with canon test results.

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